

Utilization of Qualitative Methods in Research Universities

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Abstract

This article aims to analyse the use of qualitative methods by students in carrying out their studies at Iqra Buru University, then explained about information, reason, and the orientation they have about qualitative methods. The approach used in this study is descriptive qualitative, by using interviews as a data collection model and data analysis techniques in the form of textual analysis techniques from the results of field note transcripts. Results from the field show the theoretical information of the qualitative methods possessed by informants is still low causing reasons for use because the field of science is studied, while the orientation of informants prioritizes the use of qualitative methods to complete the final task. Conclusions from field studies show that the use of qualitative methods is still considered a complement in the completion of the informant's study, so it is difficult to get research results that have contributed to the development of qualitative methods.

Keywords

Utilization, Qualitative Methods, Research Universities, Iqra Buru University

1. Introduction

University of Iqra Buru as a higher education institution in the province of Maluku (Indonesia) set the devotion of the university which include education, research and community services with the aim of, Iqra Buru University students to have academic ability to suit the needs of the world of work. Thesis is the final assignment in the form of research to do a prospective undergraduate. Similarly, the quality of University research will be seen through the results of thesis students.

Research by students at the college requires a clear method (Smith and Shaw), in this case there are two methods of research i.e. qualitative methods and quantitative methods. Qualitative research model domination often occurs on University students of social sciences as a convenience that is owned by that method (Eden and Ackermann). Term qualitative research according to Kirk & Miler originally a qualitative observations on disputed with quantitative observations (Booth et al.). They interpret qualitative method is a certain tradition in social science is fundamentally dependent observations to man in the relationship between the people (Gallopín).

Nanis Susanti in the research about qualitative research paradigms in business, many models of consumer research suggests that on going qualitative studies as well as some businesses are starting to learn, develop, filter, as well as the need to apply qualitative research methods (Susanti). In the meantime, Ihwan indicates that qualitative methods can now be accepted for consumer research and the broader field of marketing, offers its research methods from the perspective of qualitative and some possible marketing research and its application in the measurement of business performance (Batubara).

The orientation of previous research use of qualitative methods favor on more specific segmentation, as the development of qualitative methods for business research and marketing as well as the use of secondary data as a data source in the explanation of the subject matter of. This study is an overview of the use of qualitative methods by students focused discussion of actions and knowledge in choosing and applying qualitative methods as an approach to complete the final assignment.

Understanding the results of previous research that has been done, then the researchers in this study raised the issue of how the pattern of election of the research methods for the settlement of the final project by students. The objectives to be achieved from these problems is to map the knowledge of students about qualitative methods as well as explaining the factor endowments as well as a barrier to the use of qualitative methods in students at the University of Iqra Buru.

2. Research methods

Research was carried out on 5 faculty in University of Iqra Buru. The selection of informants are done at random by the consideration that the informant has been selected to represent the characteristics of the students including the following:; students of the Faculty of agriculture and forestry, economics, Faculty of teacher training and educational sciences, Faculty of law and Faculty of letters, the selected informer is the final level of the student in the process of writing the final report of the research. The time used in this research is for 60 (sixty) calendar days, beginning in the month of July to September 2018.

Main data sources in this study are words and actions, the rest is additional data such as the documentation photographs, recordings and other similar writings. With regard to data, its type can be divided into words and action, the data source is written, photo and stats (Maxwell and Reybold) (Ortiz). In this study the author's data gathering techniques use in-depth interviews was with students at 5 faculties and observation activities related directly to the informant research (Castleberry and Nolen). By utilizing custom student who likes to congregate at night, then the interview is done starting at 19.00-23.00.

For data analysis, the author uses at the time of data collection takes place, and after the completion of data collection within a certain period. By analyzing data while collecting, the writer can know first hand the lack of data should be collected as well as methods to do next in order to obtained the results of a comprehensive (Kelley-Quon). By doing the presentation of data, researchers can work more quickly and precisely in coding and decision making based on the focus of the research. The presentation of the data is an integral part of data analysis qualitative research. Presentation of data analysis as part of the reduction was also part of data analysis (Kelley-Quon) (Najmah). The presentation of data in qualitative research in General IE matrix, graphs, charts, and text narrative. The withdrawal of the conclusion is the end of the analysis of qualitative research data. The withdrawal was done with such conclusions through reflection data (Castleberry and Nolen).

3. Result And Discussion

At the end of the process of learning in College, students were assigned to create a work in the form of scientific research that is often referred to with theses (Busse et al.). So did the students Iqra Buru University was assigned to make a research to bolster knowledge in the disciplines studied, to build the culture of the learner in College, is one of the smart solutions to improve the quality of higher education (Szyjewska-Bagińska and Szyjewski). Potential instructors and students should be developed in a balanced way so as not to overlap each other. Because the basic potential of 3, i.e., moral, intellectual, and physical (Somantri) is a unitary whole which needs to be developed. So in effect they are capable of thinking, understanding and implementing what it wants with a focus (Czernek-Marszałek). Thesis as a form of application relating to the requirement that they should do research that is charged for 3 to 6 months. Here are presented the number of students who do research in the period of May to July 2018.

Table 1. Number of students who do research for final project

Faculty	Total	Percentage %
Agriculture and forestry	9	15,51
Economy	17	29,31
Law	6	10,34
Education science	21	36,20
Literature	5	8,62
n	58	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2018

University of Iqra Buru consists of 8 Faculties and has 17 courses that are scattered in several disciplines. Data tables show that the informant made a dominant sample is a social studies students which reach 49 people (84.413%)The number of students who do the most research comes from the Faculty science education as much as 21 people (36,206%), In addition they also recorded as the faculty that has the largest number of students at the University of Iqra Buru. Meanwhile, the Faculty of letters in the table are recorded only 5 people who made the informant and the fact they as Faculty of the least number of students.

Understanding the choice of research methods by students to complete a final project then researchers spread the instrument to be able to know the number of options against qualitative methods, quantitative as well as a mixture of both of these methods. Presented the following data on the percentage of students in choosing research methods.

Table 2. Percentage of students in choosing research methods for final project

Faculty	Method		
	Qualitative	Quantitative	Mixed
Agriculture and forestry	2	6	1
Economy	7	8	2
Law	5	0	1
Education science	15	3	3
Literature	4	0	1
N=58	56,89 %	29,31 %	13,79 %

Source: Primary data processed in 2018

From table that is displayed, student looks prefer qualitative methods in resolving the final assignment. Students of the Faculty of teacher training and education was recorded as informants the most widely using qualitative methods. In the background the classification proposed by the student, election against qualitative methods is caused by several factors namely; The ease in doing analysis, data collection and of processing as well as the required references are relatively easy to find.

As we know, Research has an important role in supporting any form of human activity (Castleberry and Nolen), including the results of research released by institutions like the University of Iqra Buru, among the role of study can be understood as follows; Research as a problem solver, improving human capacity in understanding the phenomena of a problem are complex and interlinked (FitzPatrick), give an answer to the question in field is examined, as well as improving the ability to explain the phenomenon of a problem, providing knowledge, Although the results sometimes cannot be directly used.

The reality imaged through the 3 reasons delivered informant, gave the signal for researchers that for the vast majority of students at the University of Iqra Buru assume data analysis in qualitative methods is still easily done, the analysis conducted just read over and over again, and expected to find the particulars that could be considered to present a phenomenon examined. Qualitative data is usually in the form of words rather than numbers, and has always been a staple of some fields in the social sciences, especially anthropology, history and political science (Yeomans). According To Bogdan, data analysis is the process of finding and compiling systematic data obtained from field notes, interviews, and other materials, making it easy to understand, and his findings can be communicated to others (Ampt and Ruiz). The analysis is done by organizing the data, elaborating into units, doing the synthesis, compiling into a pattern, choose which are important and which will be studied, and make conclusions which can be told to others (Qu and Dumay), to associate with the field, then the results of data analysis used by the student hasn't been ideal conditions as qualitative research instrument, due to the level of student understanding over how data analysis in qualitative methods.

More about the ease of collecting and processing the data into factor towing for students to prefer Qualitative methods, description of the reason can be seen from the explanation of informants indicated the interview as an easy way to get your data and compiled a transcript as an efficient way for data processing, While on other parts of a qualitative researchers are required to carefully collect field data. This is particularly troublesome because not every interesting and significant research problems for easy data search. data in field can be mapped into 4 domains (Lander et al.): front stage-disclosed (FSD), back stage-disclosed (BSD), front stage-enclosed(FSE), and back stage-enclosed (BSE) (Bryman). Student positions are on Front stage-disclosed, in the realm of data FSD data relatively easily obtained and collected. In the realm of data, qualitative researchers FSD beginners who are not very experienced can get information because it takes only the data that is on the surface. For example, the data source associated with the age and employment (except for certain works that are illegal/violates the norm) could have easily obtained a qualitative researcher.

On the third part namely ease student Iqra Buru get the reference in the conduct of qualitative research is not considered too difficult, so the process of use of theory to the analysis of the findings of the field easier. In some studies the use of literature in qualitative research is lacking usability is important to behind their research conducted, study literature at least give benefits to increase sensitivity theory researchers to identify the things that are important to data and understand it (Creswell). This capability would facilitate the formulation of an appropriate theory with the reality of the phenomena examined. By reading and studying the results of previous studies, sensitivity of researchers towards the subject of what to look for are examined for the better (FitzPatrick). With better sensitivity, researchers can plan and compiled a list of more significant for the interview asked to participants (Taylor et al.). The following is a table of accumulated reason students prefer qualitative methods.

Table 3. Reasons students choose a qualitative method for final project

Faculty	Reason for choosing		
	Analysis	Collection and processing of data	Reference
Agriculture and forestry	1	1	0
Economy	2	4	1
Law	3	1	1
Education science	2	11	2
Literature	1	2	1
N=33	27,27 %	57,57 %	15,15%

Source: Primary data processed in 2018

Based on previous reviews, Note that three factors (analysis, collection and processing of data as well as reference) be attractive for students doing research with qualitative approach. For those interesting Factor is certainly the must have convenience and compatibility with their ability. When the informant is confronted with the qualitative research instrument which researchers collated from various sources occur then the backlash against the understanding presented in the document provided. So the identification of researchers against the factors of particular interest is the ease and simplification of understanding of qualitative research methods according to informants.

On the other part, researchers not only to look at the factors of towing for students in using qualitative methods research approach as yet more of that researchers look at the obstacles encountered by students in using qualitative methods. Presented the following table regarding the obstacle of students in using qualitative methods research approach.

Table 4. Obstacles students in using qualitative methods

Faculty	Barriers		
	Transcripts	Theory	Report
Agriculture and forestry	1	0	1
Economy	1	3	3
Law	1	2	2
Education science	3	9	3
Literature	1	1	2
N=33	21,21	45,45	33,33

Source: Primary data processed in 2018

Table 4 shows that the largest obstacles found on the use of the theory of 45.454%, to informants considered the factors that hinder the completion of the final project-related use of qualitative methods. In the elaboration of results the interview the author finds an understanding of students who consider the theory as a way of strengthening and justification of focus problems researched so sought the same theory with the phenomenon researched. The author understands the use of the relevant literature in qualitative research is to endorse the accuracy of the results of the findings of the research conducted, especially on qualitative research that tests the validity of a theory. With the use of existing literature, should informants can shed some light on various rationalization of the existence of differences and similarities of the theory or concept that is a result of the findings of research conducted with the theory or concept in the previous literature not vice versa impose similarity theory with object or the problems examined (Eden and Ackermann).

In addition to theory, transcript (21.21%) and research reports (33.33%) regarded as an obstacle in the use of qualitative methods, from the interviews the author of auto summary, students seen trouble to compile the results of the interview transcript to made in the form of data. As for report, student difficulties with formatting and academic rules require that each report must adjust. The author's understanding of qualitative methods against the more descriptive analysis, this review of how to collect and collate the results of the interviews into a transcript, It's been a lot of digital technology enabling researchers in transferring voice data to writing (Smith and Shaw). Authors see this condition not as a barrier to the qualitative methods in yet more adjustments to the results on technological developments. For research reports, the difficulty is not included in the implementation of the research method but is a rule drawn up by the institution in order to facilitate comprehension and readability of the results of research conducted a student.

4. Conclusion

Qualitative methods is one of the approaches used in making the students final assignment at the University of Iqra Buru. On the selection of research methods, the average student Iqra Buru prefer qualitative method by passing three main reasons. 3 main reasons i.e.ease of data analysis field, the process of collecting and processing data as well as the ease of getting a reference supporting the research process. The ease with which it is intended as a result of the implementation of the students against the interpretation of research related qualitative understanding they get during the process of learning at the University of Iqra Buru.

The obstacles in the use of research methods in the form of interviews into a copy of the transcript, use of theory and the making the final report. For the making of transcripts, students still skimpy against the use and adjustments against facilities that make it easy to transfer digital data into interview transcript. The theory is the drag caused by the element of coercion against the theory with the phenomenon researched. To report form, drag caused by the factor of institution regulation for ease in understanding the content of research conducted by the student.

The limitations of an understanding of qualitative research into the main base of the students explain the ease and barriers in applying a qualitative approach to completion of the final project. Information and availability of the literature about qualitative research methods are the cause of the occurrence of such limitations. This research has yet to include the use of these kinds of approaches in qualitative methods such as Phenomenology, case studies, ethnography, grounded theory and so is expected to devote the existence of advanced research were able to elaborate on the use of more specific about research methods among college students.

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Biographies

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Sjaid S Fais Assagaf is one of the technical faculty lecturers of Iqra Buru University who chose to concentrate on the social field of agriculture. Completed undergraduate studies on Indonesian Muslim universities with the development of community infrastructure research. Currently still running research activities on empowering and diversification of agriculture focused on rural areas.

Iskandar Hamid is an agricultural faculty lecturer at Iqra Buru University who is always involved in community development research. Completed agricultural studies at Pattimura Ambon University with a focus on research of community development through local farming. Some research on community development continues to be done with the university research team. Currently still served as Dean of Agricultural Faculty of University Iqra Buru by continuing to develop local agricultural culture research.

M Bula is a lecturer in the technical faculty of Iqra Buru University with the specifications of the small business industry for local communities. Active on community empowerment activities as well as teaching entrepreneurship courses. Completed the study of Master of Industrial Engineering in Universitas Brawijaya Malang. Currently involved in research development of potential village community in the district Buru.

Mansyur Nawawi was a lecturer who served in the Faculty of Law of the university Iqra Buru. Completed a humanities study at the University of Gajah Mada with public law studies. Mansyur is part of a university research team that participates in community empowerment through cultural education developed by the Center for Planning and Community Development studies. One of the results of research studies published is the role of local culture in community empowerment.

Sukainap Pulhehe is a lecturer at the Faculty of Law of the University of Iqra Buru who has just completed his Master of Law studies at Pattimura University. The scientific specifications developed are the development of rural communities law studied through cultural studies. Currently still completing the research of community Development supported by the University Research Institute Iqra Buru

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